

How Agroforestry Can Improve Water Quality on Irish Farms

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Explaining how trees can benefit water quality (Photo: O’Gorman Photography- Teagasc) Teagasc staff demonstrate how trees can deliver on-farm water quality improvements

A key challenge for Irish agriculture is preventing nutrients e.g. phosphorus (P) on poorly draining soils, and sediment from entering watercourses. Strategic tree planting intercepts runoff, filtering pollutants before they reach water bodies. Grant support for agroforestry is available through the state’s Afforestation Grant and Premium Scheme, helping farmers integrate trees into their land.

Fenced-off riparian buffers slow and filter runoff, while tree roots enhance soil drainage, reducing flooding after heavy rain. Small tree groups and riparian woodlands create habitats for insects, fish, and aquatic organisms, improving Irish watercourses. Pollution Impact Potential (PIP) maps can identify high-risk areas, guiding strategic tree planting to protect water quality and biodiversity.

Riparian woodlands provide shade, regulating water temperatures for aquatic life. The Woodlands for Water and Agroforestry schemes combine setback zones with native woodland planting, boosting biodiversity and water protection. Native species such as Oak, Birch, Cherry, Alder, Hazel, and Rowan support pollinators and wildlife, strengthening ecosystems.

Soil erosion and bank collapse threaten aquatic habitats and drinking water supplies. Grassy vegetation and tree roots stabilize banks, preventing sediment runoff into rivers and lakes. Agroforestry can reduce flood risks by absorbing and slowing water flow. Soils under trees can infiltrate water up to 60 times faster than grazed pasture, minimizing runoff and downstream flooding. Tree canopies intercept rainfall, reducing stormwater impact and the need for dredging.

By incorporating agroforestry into water catchment management, Irish farmers can enhance flood control, water quality, and biodiversity, supporting sustainable farming and environmental goals.

References
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